

DCLead is an Erasmus Mundus
Joint Master Degree (EMJMD)

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

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Submission:
**Social Science
Research Methods**

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January 2024

QUALITATIVE CONTENT ANALYSIS THROUGH THE LENS OF INCLUSIVITY

Open Educational Research Project

M.A. DCLead Policy and Innovation in Europe

Abstract

This content analysis guide will elucidate the concept of qualitative content analysis by tracing its historical evolution, while also exploring strategies to mitigate biases and address the issue of representation gaps in the analytical process, while providing strategies that aim to result in a more inclusive interpretation of qualitative data.

Introduction

As social sciences such as psychology, sociology, and economics began to exponentially increase as fields of interest in the 20th century, much of their valuable data and information were lost in the quantitative methods that social science research findings were being presented in. Before this shift around the 1920s, the traditional, well-established research methods were quantitative because the results are easy to evaluate and present on a chart or graph. Many fields and industries felt that the best way to show results was with the numbers. However, things changed by 1945. Researchers like the father of qualitative research Paul Felix Lazarsfeld and Siegfried Kracauer began to show the world the value of deriving qualitative data which can be assessed, interpreted, and presented just as effectively and convincingly as quantitative data (Kuckartz, 2019).

Kracauer, who coined the term, defines “qualitative analysis” as:

Qualitative analysis by definition differs from quantitative analysis in that it achieves its breakdowns without special regard for frequencies. What counts alone in qualitative analysis – if the verb is permissible in a context which defies counting – is the selection and rational organization of such categories as condense the substantive meanings of the given text, with a view to testing pertinent assumptions and hypotheses (Kracauer, 1952).

Methodological Background

Qualitative methods can be used in research contexts where exploration and interpretation of data is essential and the researcher aims to collect insightful data about participants' experiences, perspectives, or nuanced meanings; information that is not necessarily measurable in a quantitative sense. However, it is important to note that content analysis is not exclusively qualitative and can invite quantitative findings as well. While there are many qualitative research techniques like focus groups, which allow the researcher to collect data about the beliefs, attitudes, or assumptions of participants; interviews, which can be semi-structured in order to focus on a specific topic or in-depth to truly understand the participants' experiences of perspectives, here we focus on the content analysis of texts, including but not limited to journals, online discussions, and articles (Hammarberg et. al, 2016).

Content analysis is an appropriate choice of research method if a researcher is attempting to identify attitudes, behaviors, and trends of individuals and groups, analyze their psychological

states, reveal patterns and differences, test concepts and theories before creating or when evaluating the results of other research instruments like surveys, interviews and focus groups (Content Analysis Methods and Examples, 2023).

Organization of Qualitative Data

Throughout each step of the process of content analysis, organization is crucial to ensure systematic and efficient analysis of the data. The organizational process begins with familiarization of the content that is being analyzed. Commonly used styles for analyzing qualitative data include constant comparison and thematic analysis, but here we will discuss the style of coding and categorization (Harding & Whitehead, 2016).

Recurring themes, concepts, and patterns can be identified to create a systematic coding process. The two basic methods for coding include line-by-line code, in which words and phrases are carefully examined, or by scanning paragraphs for variables relevant to the research question. After either method, the codes can be arranged in a hierarchical structure of categories and themes in order to identify the relationship between different elements in a process called categorization (Harding & Whitehead, 2016).

Researchers may also create matrices or charts to visualize connections and patterns in order to better comprehend the data. Throughout this process, maintaining detailed and well-documented records of decisions and interpretations is essential for transparency and the replication of the analysis. Ultimately, a well-organized qualitative content analysis dataset allows for the extraction of meaningful insights and facilitates the synthesis of findings in a coherent and interpretable manner.

Utilizing qualitative data analysis software (QDAS) can streamline this process by enabling systematic sorting and creating a codebook. Content analysis software facilitates the examination and organization of large volumes of textual or visual data, streamlining the process of extracting patterns, themes, and insights. The general workflow of content analysis software involves the following key steps:

After the researcher imports the data, including text documents, images, or audio, into the software where it is preprocessed for standardization and readability. Afterwards, the software uses a coding system to label the data based on concepts or variables and provides tools to apply the codes. After the data has been coded, the QDAS programs generate a report summarizing the findings while including visual representations of the data input through graphs and charts (Friese, 2019). Popular content analysis software tools include NVivo, MAXQDA, ATLAS.ti, and Dedoose. These tools are designed to accommodate various research methodologies and offer a range of features to support the analysis of qualitative data (8 Great Tools).

Racial Bias and Issue of Representation Gaps

A crucial aspect to consider when doing qualitative content analysis is that biases may be especially prevalent due to the subjective and interpretative nature of the method. Because “bias can stem from systemic, institutional, interpersonal or individual forms of prejudice against a socially-defined race or ethnicity” (p. 1), it can affect the research results and framing greatly. Prejudice could look like a lack of diversity on the research team, misunderstandings in language, unintentional preference for one group over another, or even the conflation of race and biology. This can often be seen in healthcare fields; ancestry and genetics can affect health, but this is not to be linked to race, as it is a societal construct rather than a biological factor (Naicker & Nunan, 2023).

The underrepresentation of minorities in research is exacerbated by algorithms which perpetuate racial biases (Naicker & Nunan, 2023), making this both a social issue and an algorithmic issue. Content analysis software, although valuable for streamlining data analysis, can pose challenges related to bias and lack of racial or gender inclusivity. These tools may inherit or perpetuate biases present in the data they are trained on, reflecting and potentially exacerbating societal prejudices. Due to the lack of diversity amongst program developers in the past, there are biases embedded in these systems (Broussard, 2018). Predefined dictionaries or sentiment analysis algorithms within these software systems may not adequately capture the nuances of diverse languages, cultures, or expressions, leading to skewed interpretations. Additionally, the coding frameworks embedded in the software may not account for intersectionality, overlooking the complexity of experiences shaped by the intersection of race, gender, and other social factors. Furthermore, the development teams behind content analysis software may lack diversity, resulting in a limited range of perspectives and potential oversight of biases during the tool's design and implementation (Broussard, 2018).

While qualitative content analysis software can offer efficiency and organization in handling large datasets, there are instances where manual gathering proves advantageous. Manual qualitative content analysis allows a diverse set of researchers to directly engage with the data during the coding process, fostering a deeper understanding of the nuances, context, and subtleties that might be overlooked by automated tools. Human intuition and interpretative skills are crucial in capturing the intricate layers of meaning within qualitative data, and machines will never fully be able to replicate these skills (Broussard, 2018). The flexibility of manual analysis allows for dynamic adjustments in coding schemes as insights evolve throughout the research process. Researchers can employ their subjectivity and expertise to discern patterns and connections that may not be immediately apparent, promoting a more nuanced and context-sensitive interpretation. Additionally, the absence of reliance on software can reduce the risk of algorithmic biases and ensure a more transparent and reflexive research approach. While software can be valuable, the manual gathering of qualitative content analysis data can contribute to a positive cycle of machine learning from good quality data in order to reinvent the future by “creating Big Data models that follow our ethical lead” (O’Neil, 2016).

While it is a challenge to completely remove all bias from qualitative data analysis, there are many strategies to mitigate biases and prioritize inclusivity. The first step is adopting a reflexive approach throughout the research process, which allows the analyst to continually reflect on their own perspectives and potential biases. This self-awareness contributes to a more

transparent and nuanced interpretation of the data. Another strategy is diversity on the coding team by including people of different cultures, communities, or ethnic or racial backgrounds in the process of data coding. By having multiple perspectives in interpretations, you can prevent one-sidedness. Establishing clear and predefined coding categories based on well-defined criteria helps maintain consistency and objectivity so that when compared, similarities should arise indicating that the coders have reached some mutual agreement. Triangulation is crucial; researchers ensure that multiple sources of data can support your interpretation (Avoiding Bias, 2023).

Another important consideration to take into account is the source of the content. Who are the authors, where was it written, and with what positions? If possible, reaching out to the original source can provide some clarity and perspective on a researcher's interpretation, or can help the researcher understand the background of the source from where the content originated. To address representation gaps, deliberate efforts should be made to ensure that the sample under analysis is diverse and inclusive, capturing a wide range of voices and experiences. Regularly reassessing and refining coding schemes in collaboration with stakeholders can further enhance the accuracy and relevance of the analysis, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the qualitative data. Researchers should also consider the reasons they obtained their specific data in order to rule out or account for alternative explanations. Last but not least, researchers can share results with their peers and include the perspectives of others from various backgrounds in order to locate gaps in argumentation that need to be addressed (Avoiding Bias, 2023).

Conclusion

In conclusion, qualitative content analysis is a powerful tool in social science research, offering a nuanced understanding of data beyond quantitative metrics. While the historical shift to valuing inclusive qualitative methods marked a transformative era in research, problems including biases and lack of representation minorities are still prevalent in research. This guide attempts to highlight the necessity of awareness in the analytical process regarding biases and representation gaps. Employing diverse coding teams, refining coding schemes, and engaging in constant reflection are important strategies in mitigating biases. The challenges posed by content analysis software demand careful consideration, advocating for a balanced integration of manual analysis to ensure a holistic, transparent, and ethically sound approach in unraveling the complexities of qualitative data.

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